

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Adding and Updating 3D Reference Objects in the NIH3D Portal

Overview of the process of adding and updating assets on NIH3D

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Introduction

Three-dimensional (3D) reference objects from the Human Reference Atlas (HRA) are held in the National Institutes of Health (NIH) 3D repository (National Institute of Health 2025), where they can be accessed and used by other researchers and general audiences. This increases the reach of the HRA and helps ensure that this collection of assets will be supported after funding ends.

The HRA collection is revised and expanded every six months as part of the HRA release process. This SOP documents how to add and update assets in NIH 3D so that the repository contains the latest published versions of the HRA collection. The primary audience for this SOP is the HRA Integrator who updates this collection, but the SOP may also be of interest for people wishing to use these digital objects or users interested in uploading their own objects to this NIH repository.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **Center Assistant** maintains usernames and passwords for CNS access to NIH 3D.

The **HRA Integrator** is responsible for updating the HRA collection available through NIH 3D each time there is an HRA release, typically every six months.

The **HRA Lead** is responsible for reviewing and approving the release of uploaded reference objects.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Center Assistant	Traci Smith	cnscntr@iu.edu
HRA Integrator	Hrishikesh Mulkutkar	infoccf@iu.edu

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HRA Lead	Katy Börner	katy@iu.edu
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Procedures

The asset collection is updated every six months, following each release of the Human Reference Atlas. New and revised 3D reference objects are updated on the NIH 3D portal.

NIH 3D is a community-based portal for sharing bioscientific and medical 3D models. Models available via this portal are used for 3D printing and interactive visualization on the web and in virtual or augmented reality user interfaces. The 3D reference objects from the Human Reference Atlas are available via this portal via an HRA collection at <https://3d.nih.gov/collections/hra>.

Logging in and accessing the HRA collection

- Obtain email and password login credentials from the Center Assistant.
- Navigate to the NIH 3D website, which is located at <https://3d.nih.gov>, see **Fig. 1**.

Figure 1. Landing page for NIH 3D.

- Click on the Sign in button at the top right of the page to get to the login screen, see **Fig. 2**.

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Figure 2. Logging into NIH 3D.

- Enter the email and password to login.
- Once logged in, search for HRA in the search bar at the top of the page. This will return all the models related to the HRA.
- Alternatively, you can click on the profile icon at the top right of the page, then click on Profile & Submission Dashboard (see **Fig. 3**) to access all the models, published and unpublished, as well as builds (see **Fig. 4**). Only published models should be shared.

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Figure 3. Profile & Submission Dashboard.

Figure 4. Updating specific organ models.

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Updating existing assets on NIH 3D

For 3D reference objects that were revised during a recent release, update the corresponding file in NIH 3D.

- Click on the model you want to edit or update (see **Fig. 5**). Update any file that was revised in the recent HRA release.
 - Go to the 3D Reference Object Library at <https://humanatlas.io/3d-reference-library>.
 - Select the latest HRA version, then download all organs published in the recent release.
- New models included in the latest release can be updated by clicking on the Submit button in the toolbar of the portal to add new files under organ illustration.
- Update metadata as necessary, using the HRA Knowledge Graph (KG), found at <https://lod.humanatlas.io/ref-organ>, as the source of truth.

Figure 5. Asset view page on NIH 3D.

- Add each file to one of the respective subcollections.
 - Click on the Add to collection button and select the relevant Human Reference Atlas subcollection, e.g., male or female (see **Fig. 6**).

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Figure 6. Assigning assets to the HRA collection.

Adding new assets to NIH 3D

When new 3D reference objects are added to the HRA, upload these new 3D reference objects to NIH 3D.

- Click on the Submit button in the toolbar of the portal to add new files under Submit a Model option.
- Choose the Anatomy category, as illustrated in **Fig. 7**, once on the landing page.

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Choose one of these two options

QuickSubmit: Generate 3D models from an existing experimental structure database

Enter an identification code from the Protein Data Bank(PDB), the Electron Microscopy Databank(EMDB), PubChem or AlphaFold. NIH 3D will retrieve the structure and supporting information, then create 3D meshes. This type of submission is automatically published.

PDB ▼

PDB IDs have two formats: 4 characters (e.g., 6VXX) or 8 characters (e.g., PDB-xxxxxxx)

Submit→

Upload a file from one of the following categories

Note: this is a multi-step process. You will have the option to save your information and return to it later.

- **Step One:** Submit one or more files and some general information about the entry.
- **Step Two:** Once our workflows have processed the files, you will be invited to provide more information and/or supplementary files to support your entry.
- **Step Three:** Publish or save your entry.

🦴

Anatomy
zip of dcm files, glb, stl, wrl, x3d

🔧

Devices & Hardware
glb, stl, wrl, x3d

🦿

Prosthetics & Assistive Devices
glb, stl, wrl, x3d

🧪

Molecules

cif, pdb, pdb1, mae, mol2, mol, sdf, map, omap, tif, tiff, cif.gz, map.gz, glb, stl, wrl, x3d

Figure 7. Landing Page - choose Anatomy.

- Upload the file using the Upload file(s) dialogue box as illustrated in **Fig. 8**.

v1.0.0

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Upload file(s)
Next: Entry details Next→

Please upload the files that you would like to have processed by NIH 3D.

Our workflows will accept:
- Mesh files: **glb, stl, wrl, x3d**

Medical images in DICOM format:
The **.dcm** files must be sequential in a single folder that has been compressed into a .zip
You must follow the file structure below:

```
dicoms.zip
|— image01.dcm
|— image02.dcm
|— image03.dcm
```

We are only processing **CT Scans**. Other scan types will fail.
Wedo not permit sharing datasets containing the entire face
Ensure filenames consist of only alphanumeric characters, excluding special characters such as 0, [], and {}.

UPLOAD FILE(S)

Drop files here or browse files

Figure 8. Upload the .GLB file.

- Once uploaded, give it a suitable label preferably following previous conventions where the label is given as: `vh-<gender>-<organ name>-<left or right orientation>`.
- Do not enter any other information and click the Next button.

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The screenshot shows a web form titled "Tell us about your entry" with a "Next: Submit" button. The form is divided into four main sections:

- Title***: A text input field with the instruction "Enter a short descriptive title for your submission".
- Description***: A rich text editor with a toolbar containing options for Normal, Bold (B), Italic (I), Underline (U), Strikethrough (ABC), Bulleted List, Numbered List, Indent Left, Indent Right, Decrease Indent, Increase Indent, Text Color (A), Background Color, Link, and Unlink. Below the editor is the instruction "Tell us about your submission. Some details might include what it represents, what it was made for, special instructions for 3D printing...".
- Keywords***: A text input field with the instruction "Enter up to 10 comma-separated keywords".
- License***: A dropdown menu currently set to "CC-BY". Below it is the instruction "Select a license to give others the right to reuse, remix, or redistribute your contributed 3D model. For more information visit [CreativeCommons.org](https://creativecommons.org)".

Figure 9. Update metadata.

- Update metadata as necessary (see **Fig. 9**), using the HRA Knowledge Graph (KG), found at <https://lod.humanatlas.io/ref-organ>, as the source of truth.
- Add keywords as necessary. Usually HRA, Human Reference Atlas, human, <organ name>, <FTU name> are tagged as keywords.
- Do not enter any other information and click the Next button.
- Click on the Submit your model button, as shown in **Fig. 10**, and the model will be built for submission.

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Figure 10. Click on the Submit your model button and the model will be built for submission.

- Once submitted—within a few minutes—the model will be built and you will receive an email with confirmation that the model has been built successfully.
- You can click on the link attached in your email to view the model and update any metadata. If necessary, add Maya as 3D modeling software in the same tab where metadata was updated.
- If there are no edits click the Next button in all the tabs.
- Finally, you will reach the Publish page where you can click on the Publish Model button to publish your model (see **Fig. 11**).

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Figure 11. Publishing the model.

- Add each file to one of the respective subcollections (see Fig. 13).
 - Click on the Add to collection button and select the relevant Human Reference Atlas subcollection, e.g., male or female.

Figure 13. Assigning assets to the HRA collection.

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References and Resources

National Institute of Health. 2025. "NIH 3D." <https://3d.nih.gov>.

Glossary

3D reference object: Polygon mesh of 3D spatial objects (e.g., anatomical structures), their object node hierarchy, materials, and surface color and texture. They are created by medical illustrators with the involvement of subject matter experts following standard operating procedures.

functional tissue unit (FTU): A functional tissue unit is the smallest tissue organization, i.e., a set of cells, that performs a unique physiologic function and is replicated multiple times in a whole organ. FTUs can be hierarchically nested.

Human Reference Atlas (HRA): The Human Reference Atlas is a comprehensive, high-resolution, three-dimensional, multiscale atlas of all the cells in the healthy human body. The Human Reference Atlas provides standard terminologies and data structures for describing specimens, biological structures, and spatial positions linked to existing ontologies.

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